

International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes

EB-ICSP Meeting August 31st 2023 - Minutes

Minute 1. Call to order

Chair:
E.R.B. MOORE
University of Gothenburg
Sweden

The Chair called the meeting to order at 9.00 a.m. UK time.

Minute 2. Record of attendance

Vice-Chair:
C.M. MANAIA
Universidade Católica Portuguesa
Portugal

The following members of the Executive Board participated: I.C. Sutcliffe (Chair), E.R.B. Moore (Vice-Chair), A. Oren (Executive Secretary), S.L.W. On (Secretary of Subcommittees), P. Nielsen (Treasurer), Y. Shouche (Member-at-Large) and M. Göker (Secretary JC). C. Manaia (Vice-Chair elect) joined the meeting as an observer. Apologies were received from R. Hahnke (Member-at-Large) H. Christensen (Vice-Chair JC), and M. Sakamoto (Member-at-Large elect).

Executive Secretary:
A. OREN
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
Israel

Secretary for Subcommittees:
S.L.W. ON
Lincoln University
New Zealand

Minute 3. Welcoming C. Manaia

I.C. Sutcliffe welcomed C. Manaia (Vice-Chair elect) who participated in the meeting as an observer.

Treasurer:
P. NIELSEN
Novozymes, Copenhagen
Denmark

Minute 4. Minutes of the 3rd August 2023 meeting of the Executive Board

The draft minutes of the 3rd August 2023 meeting were approved with a minor corrections. No redaction was needed. A. Oren will distribute the unredacted minutes to the members of the ICSP, the Judicial Commission, and chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy, and he will send a copy to E.R.B. Moore to be posted on the ICSP website.

Members at Large:

R. HAHNKE
Leibniz Institute DSMZ
Germany

M. SAKAMOTO
RIKEN BioResource
Research Center
Japan

Members of the Judicial Committee

Chair:
D.R. ARAHAL
University of Valencia
Spain

Vice-Chair:
H. CHRISTENSEN
University of Copenhagen
Denmark

Secretary:
M. GÖKER
Leibniz Institute DSMZ
Germany

Minute 5. Matters Arising/Action points from previous meetings

- A. Oren has forwarded the minutes of the 29th June 2023 meeting to all members of the ICSP, the Judicial Commission and the chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy.

- E.R.B. Moore did not yet post the minutes of the 29th June 2023 meeting of the Executive Board on the ICSP website. Ongoing.

- E.R.B. Moore posted the short CVs of some of the deceased Life Members of the ICSP on the ICSP website but did not yet complete the postings. Ongoing.

- I.C. Sutcliffe and A. Oren have prepared a new draft revision of the ICSP statutes. The document including a table, comparing the current version of the statutes with the proposed revision, and provides space for comments. See Minute 8. I.C. Sutcliffe has sent the proposed new section on the ICSP membership structure to R. Samson (Executive Secretary of IUMS) for comments.

- E.R.B. Moore did not yet post the minutes of the 24th January meeting of the Publications Committee on the ICSP website; expected to be posted in the next week. Ongoing.

- E.R.B. Moore organised with D. Cardew to meet with M. Göker at some date in the next week, to discuss possible changes to be made in the way the ICSP website is operated, which should be further coordinated with R. Samson (Executive Secretary IUMS). Ongoing.

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- E.R.B. Moore has liaised with P.-E. Fournier to discuss the novel regulations concerning availability of biological material issued by the French government. See Minute 6.
- I.C. Sutcliffe and A. Oren have prepared the second ballot for the election of the fourth member of the 28th class of the Judicial Commission. See Minute 7.
- I.C. Sutcliffe and E.R.B. Moore have liaised with the Judicial Commission to organise the election of its new officers. A ballot for the election will be prepared and circulated among the members of the JC. See Minute 10.
- I.C. Sutcliffe and A. Oren have prepared the ballot on the proposal to include the categories kingdom and domain in the ICNP. The ballot was sent to the voting members of the ICSP on 8st August by A. Oren together with the collated comments posted on the Slack channel. E.R.B. Moore and C. Manaia serve as the tellers. See Minute 13.
- No further comments from the members of the Executive Board were received regarding the draft report to IUMS and the draft financial report by 9th August.
- A. Oren has sent the ICSP report over the period April 2020 – March 2023 and the financial report prepared by P. Nielsen to R. Rappuoli, R. Samson and H. Lawrence (Chair, Executive Secretary and Treasurer of IUMS). No response was yet received.
- S.L.W. On has not yet contacted the authors of the proposal for the establishment of a subcommittee on the taxonomy of *Borrelia* to notify them that the proposal was approved by the Executive Board. Ongoing.
- S.L.W. On prepared a draft version, but did not yet finalize, a letter to be sent to G. Greub and N. Borrel, Chair and Secretary, respectively, of the Subcommittee on Chlamydiae about concerns of the Executive Board relating to the recent proposals of the subcommittee. Ongoing.
- E.R.B. Moore did not yet liaise with M.E. Trujillo to form a new and active panel of experts that can be consulted by the IJSEM editors on matters relating to the Nagoya protocol and local restrictions on the availability of type strains. He has updated C. Manaia, who will become the new liaison between the ICSP and the IJSEM, on this topic. Ongoing.

Minute 6. New restrictions on the availability of type strains isolated in France

A Oren has corresponded with P.-E. Fournier about the new French regulations that restrict availability of biological material. The regulations are complex, and do not apply to human isolates. A. Oren will forward the relevant material to E.R.B. Moore. E.R.B. Moore has already contacted the curators of several culture collection to exchange information and ideas on how to deal with the new regulations. To date, E.R.B. Moore received response from only 1 French Culture Collection to queries about how they are handling the French law.

Minute 7. Election of new commissioners of the Judicial Commission

The voting members of the ICSP have been rebaloted for the 4th position in the 28th Class between C. Dunlap and M. del C. Montero-Calasanz. I.C. Sutcliffe and A. Oren served as the tellers. M. del C. Montero-Calasanz was elected (12 votes, vs. 9 votes for C. Dunlap). The Executive Board congratulates M. del C. Montero-Calasanz for being elected. C. Dunlap was informed by I.C. Sutcliffe of the outcome of the ballot and thanked for his engagement.

Minute 8. Proposed revision of the ICSP statutes

A. Oren has circulated a new version of the proposed revision of the ICSP statutes, prepared by A. Oren

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and I.C. Sutcliffe, and based on earlier draft versions including some of the suggestions proposed by M. Göker. The document is presented in the format of a table, comparing the current version of the statutes with the proposed revision, and provides space for comments. It was proposed that, after a consensus document is finalized, it should be submitted for publication in the IJSEM, with all members of the outgoing Executive Board as authors. However, members of the Executive Board suggested that some of the proposed changes need to be discussed further and alternative versions could be proposed. Therefore, it was decided that all members of the Executive Board should critically examine the current draft version and send any proposed changes to all board members no later than 27th September. A. Oren will collate the suggestions received and prepare a new version to be discussed during the next meeting of the Executive Board.

Minute 9. Update on Subcommittees

S.L.W. On reported that the page proofs of the minutes of the pan-subcommittee meeting held in October 2022 were corrected. The document should be published soon in the IJSEM.

Two new minutes documents were published in the past month:

Bowman J. Subcommittee on the Taxonomy of aerobic *Bacteroidetes* (formerly *Flavobacterium* and *Cytophaga*-like bacteria). Minutes of the open meeting, 10 July 2019, Glasgow, UK. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2023;73:005966.

Borrel N, Greub G, [for the ICSP Subcommittee on the taxonomy of Chlamydiae](#). Subcommittee on the taxonomy of Chlamydiae: Minutes of the closed meeting, March 20 [2023], Meeting of the Chlamydia Research Society, Omaha, NE, USA. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2023;73:006004.

It was noted that Minute 7 of the latter document contains a statement that the ICSP Subcommittee does not adopt the SeqCode.

Two subcommittees on taxonomy have recently published minutes and other documents that do not accurately reflect the rules and norms of the ICSP and, notably, Article 6 (5) of the ICSP statutes: the subcommittee on the taxonomy of Chlamydiae in the Minutes of the 25th August 2022 meeting (as noted previously, see Matters Arising) and the subcommittee on the taxonomy of Rhizobia and Agrobacteria in the minutes of the 11th October 2022 meeting of that subcommittee (*Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2023; 73:005856). S.L.W. On has drafted letters to the chairs and the secretaries of these subcommittees to explain the reservations of the ICSP Executive Board on these documents. He also will send a letter to the chairs and secretaries of all subcommittees on taxonomy to make them aware of the rules of the ICSP statutes concerning the mandate of the subcommittees.

Minute 10. Report from the Judicial Commission

M. Göker reported that the page proofs of Opinion 129 were received, and that M. del C. Montero Calasanz, who was recently elected to the Judicial Commission, has been introduced to the work of the Commission.

Nominations for the positions of chair, vice-chair and secretary were invited, and can be submitted until before 1st September. In accordance with Article 7 (b) (2) of the statutes of the ICSP, the chair of the ICSP will then organize the election of the officers of the Judicial Commission from among its members.

Minute 11. Update from Publications Committee

There were no updates.

E.R.B. Moore will coordinate with C. Manaia to try to schedule a meeting of the Publications Committee with the staff of the Microbiology Society before the end of 2023.

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Minute 12. Update from IJSEM

The annual editorial board meeting of the IJSEM will be held online on 8th September. C. Manaia, who is an editor of the journal, will also represent the ICSP as Vice-Chair and liaison of the ICSP.

A. Oren mentioned his recent correspondence with A. Pinevich (St. Petersburg), whose proposal submitted in the beginning of 2022 to emend the ICNP is still on hold. Handling was paused by the IJSEM editorial office staff because of the MS policy of a temporary moratorium on publication of research funded by the Russian state, or an author from an institution that has publicly expressed support for this war. I.C. Sutcliffe explained that, as previously discussed by the Executive Board, we must follow the decision by the Microbiology Society council, so that the ICSP cannot help Dr. Pinevich publishing his paper.

A Oren asked whether the nomenclature reviewers of the IJSEM are also entitled to an annual travel allowance of GBP 1000 like the handling editors and the list editors. This will further be discussed as an agenda point for the next Executive Board meeting. Support for such compensation for the nomenclature reviewers was expressed by several EB members.

Minute 13. Update from the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP

A Oren reported that the page proofs of the paper reporting emendation of Rules 8, 15, 22, 25a, 30(3)(b), 30(4), 34a, and Appendix 7 of the ICNP were received and corrected.

The ballot on the proposal to include the categories kingdom and domain in the ICNP is ongoing, with E.R.B. Moore and C. Manaia as the tellers. After the ballot closes on 8th September, A. Oren will prepare the outcome for publication in the IJSEM. By 31st August, 13 votes were received. The tellers will send reminders to the ICSP members who did not yet vote.

M. Göker forwarded to the Executive Board a list with a few minor errors he detected in the 2022 revision of the ICNP. A. Oren will collate these and other errors found or to be found in the document. The incoming Editorial Board of the ICNP will decide whether publication of corrigenda on a platform like Zenodo or in the IJSEM is justified before a new revision of the ICNP will be prepared.

A. Oren expressed his willingness to continue to serve as Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP during the 2023-2026 term. It was suggested to address the need of appointing an Editor-in-Chief during the next meeting.

Minute 14. Treasurer's update

P. Nielsen reported that travel expenses for A. Jones and M.E. Trujillo were approved and are being processed.

The incoming Executive Board should consider adding vice-chair C. Manaia as a signatory on the ICSP bank account.

Minute 15. Update from the working group on type strain accessibility

Y. Shouche informed the Executive Board that the Biodiversity Act of India was recently amended. Based on the information given, as per new provisions of the Act, any non-Indian accessing Indian bioresources needs only to register with the National Authority. Y. Shouche will further inquire about the details, especially the question whether registration should be sufficient and that prior approval is no longer required, and how 3rd party access should be organised. The Executive Board thanked Y. Shouche for his efforts to solve the problems caused by the Indian regulations.

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Minute 16. Update on the Singleton Deposit Initiative

M. Göker reported that he received some new information and comments from different culture collections he had contacted, but no significant new progress was made in the past months.

Minute 17. Update from the working group on Education & Outreach

The working group has shown little activity in the past months and needs to be revived. E.R.B. Moore will send invitations to colleagues who may be interested in joining the working group. Y. Shouche expressed his willingness to continue his participation.

Minute 18. Valediction

I.C. Sutcliffe, who stepped down as chair of the ICPS after two consecutive terms, thanked the Executive Board and all others who contributed to work of the ICSP in the past years. He especially mentioned the efficient work of the Judicial Commission to eliminate the large backlog of Requests for Opinions to be discussed and the Editorial Board of the ICNP for the production of the 2022 Revision of the Code; the finalization of a long-term publishing agreement with the Microbiology Society was also noted as a significant achievement this term. E.R.B. Moore thanked I.C. Sutcliffe on behalf of the Executive Board and the ICSP membership.

Minute 19 Other business

There was no other business.

Date of next meeting: 28th September; the time will be decided by the incoming Executive Board.

Adjourned at 11.05

Minutes prepared by A. Oren – 1st September 2023

Action points:

- E.R.B. Moore, to send requests for confirming the time for regular EB-ICSP meetings, to be scheduled on the last Thursday of each month.
- A. Oren, to forward the minutes of the 3rd August 2023 meeting to all members of the ICSP, the Judicial Commission and the chairs of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy.
- E.R.B. Moore, to post the minutes of the 29th June 2023 and 3rd August meetings of the Executive Board on the ICSP website.
- E.R.B. Moore, to complete the posting of short CVs of deceased Life Members on the ICSP website.
- E.R.B. Moore, to post the minutes of the 24th January meeting of the Publications Committee on the ICSP website.
- M. Göker and E.R.B. Moore, to discuss with D. Cardew possible changes to be made in the way the ICSP website is operated, which should be further coordinated with R. Samson (Executive Secretary IUMS).
- S.L.W. On, to contact the authors of the proposal for the establishment of a subcommittee on the taxonomy of *Borrelia* and notify them that the proposal was approved by the Executive Board.

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- A. Oren, to forward information received from P.-E. Fournier about the French restrictions on the availability of biological material to E.R.B. Moore.
- E.R.B. Moore and C. Manaia, to liaise with M.E. Trujillo to form a new and active panel of experts that can be consulted by the IJSEM editors on matters relating to the Nagoya protocol and local restrictions on the availability of type strains.
- All members of the Executive Board, to critically examine the proposed revisions of the ICSP statutes, and to send any proposed changes to all board members no later than 27th September.
- A. Oren, to collate the received suggestions for emendation of the statutes and prepare a new version to be discussed during the next meeting of the Executive Board.
- S.L.W. On, to finalize letters to the chairs and the secretaries of the subcommittees on the taxonomy of Chlamydiae and the subcommittee on the taxonomy of Rhizobia and Agrobacteria to explain the reservations of the ICSP Executive Board on meeting minutes published recently by these subcommittees.
- S.L.W. On, to send a letter to the chairs and secretaries of all subcommittees on taxonomy to make them aware of the rules of the ICSP statutes and rules concerning the mandate of the subcommittees as defined in Article 6 (5) of the statutes.
- E.R.B. Moore, to organize the election of the chair, vice-chair and secretary of the Judicial Commission.
- E.R.B. Moore, to schedule a meeting of the Publications Committee with the staff of the Microbiology Society, if possible before the end of 2023.
- E.R.B. Moore, to notify M. Trujillo about the new term of Officers of the EB-ICSP and that C. Manaia will be new Vice-Chair and liaison of the ICSP on the IJSEM Editorial Board and Chair of the ICSP Publications Committee.
- E.R.B. Moore, to send invitations to colleagues who may be interested to join the working group on Education and Outreach.